
**THE IMPORTANCE OF USING DIFFERENT TECHNOLOGIES IN
DEVELOPING THE CROSS-CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF YOUNG
LEARNERS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING**

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Annotation: This article explores the pivotal role of technology in fostering cross-cultural competence among young learners in the context of English language education. It argues that traditional teaching methods alone are insufficient in preparing students for today's interconnected world, where proficiency in English extends beyond language skills to include understanding and respecting diverse cultures. The integration of diverse technologies such as virtual reality, multimedia resources, online forums, and interactive apps is examined as essential in creating immersive learning environments. These environments facilitate authentic cultural experiences, promote empathy, tolerance, and respect, and enhance students' ability to communicate effectively across cultural boundaries. The article highlights the transformative impact of technology in personalizing learning experiences, breaking down geographical barriers, and preparing students to navigate and appreciate global diversity. Through a comprehensive analysis of theoretical foundations and practical applications, the article underscores the importance of technological integration in shaping culturally competent individuals who can thrive in today's globalized society.

Keywords: technology, cross-cultural competencies, interaction, communication, foreign languages

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Аннотация: Эта статья исследует решающую роль технологий в развитии межкультурной компетенции среди молодых учащихся в контексте обучения английскому языку. В ней аргументируется, что традиционные методы обучения в одиночку недостаточны для подготовки студентов к современному взаимосвязанному миру, где владение английским языком важно не только для умений языка, но и для понимания и уважения разнообразных культур. Интеграция различных технологий, таких как виртуальная реальность,

мультимедийные ресурсы, онлайн-форумы и интерактивные приложения, рассматривается как неотъемлемый элемент создания иммерсивных учебных сред. Эти среды способствуют получению подлинных культурных опытов, поощряют эмпатию, терпимость и уважение, а также улучшают способность студентов эффективно общаться в условиях культурных различий. Статья подчеркивает трансформационное влияние технологий на персонализацию учебного процесса, преодоление географических барьеров и подготовку студентов к пониманию и оценке глобального разнообразия. Через комплексный анализ теоретических основ и практических применений статья акцентирует внимание на важности интеграции технологий в формировании культурно компетентных личностей, способных успешно функционировать в современном глобализированном обществе.

Ключевые слова: технологии, межкультурная компетенция, взаимодействие, коммуникация, иностранные языки

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini o'qitish kontekstida yosh o'quvchilarda madaniyatlararo kompetentsiyani rivojlantirishda texnologiyaning muhim rolini o'rganadi. Uning ta'kidlashicha, ingliz tilini bilish til ko'nikmalaridan tashqari, turli madaniyatlarni tushunish va hurmat qilishni o'z ichiga olgan bugungi o'zaro bog'liq dunyoga talabalarni tayyorlashda faqat an'anaviy o'qitish usullari etarli emas. Virtual haqiqat, multimedia resurslari, onlayn forumlar va interaktiv ilovalar kabi turli texnologiyalarning integratsiyasi immersiv o'quv muhitini yaratishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu muhitlar haqiqiy madaniy tajribalarni osonlashtiradi, empatiya, bag'rikenglik va hurmatni rivojlantiradi va talabalarining madaniy chegaralar bo'ylab samarali muloqot qilish qobiliyatini oshiradi. Maqolada texnologiyaning o'rganish tajribasini shaxsiylashtirish, geografik to'siqlarni yo'q qilish va o'quvchilarni global xilma-xillikni tushunishga tayyorlashda o'zgartiruvchi ta'siri ta'kidlangan. Maqolada nazariy asoslar va amaliy qo'llanmalarni har tomonlama tahlil qilish orqali bugungi globallashtirilgan jamiyatda rivojlana oladigan madaniy jihatdan barkamol shaxslarni shakllantirishda texnologik integratsiya muhimligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiyalar, muloqot qilish, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, o'zaro ta'sir, muloqot, horijiy tillar.

Introduction

In today's world, people are increasingly facing the need for cooperation with representatives of other cultures. Thus, knowledge of the language of international communication is an essential aspect by which success and human education are judged. Certainly, English language teaching should be based on respect, understanding, and acceptance of cultural differences between countries of native and foreign languages. Thus, the thesis underlies the intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages, as the high level of intercultural competency has its basis in primary school. Moreover, the task of the primary school teacher is not only to help students master the curriculum but also to teach them to respect others' opinions, history, and culture of other nations, as well as help them master initial adaptation skills in a dynamically developing world.

Despite extensive research on the methodological and theoretical aspects of cultural studies across all education levels—from novice to advanced levels—there has been insufficient focus on the concept of 'intercultural competence', particularly its development through playful methods among beginners. Theoretical support for these issues involves incorporating materials that encompass communicative, sociocultural, and region-specific content aligned with contemporary professional standards. Furthermore, in the era of globalization, there is a critical need for individuals to cultivate their own intercultural communication skills and cultural competence by gaining familiarity with diverse cultures. This challenge is compounded by significant interest in cross-cultural communication within our country, yet a limited availability of suitable educational resources authored by local experts on this subject. Developing cross-cultural competence among young learners in English language teaching is increasingly recognized as essential in today's interconnected world. As societies become more diverse and interconnected, proficiency in English extends beyond language skills alone; it necessitates an understanding and appreciating of different cultures, beliefs, and practices.

Integrating various technologies into the language learning process can significantly enhance the development of cross-cultural competence. These technologies provide young learners with immersive experiences that expose them to diverse cultural perspectives, norms, and communication styles. Through interactive multimedia platforms, virtual exchanges, and online collaborations, students can engage directly with peers from different cultural backgrounds, fostering empathy, tolerance, and respect.

Furthermore, technology facilitates access to authentic cultural content, such as literature, music, and films, which enriches language learning by providing context and relevance. Digital tools empower teachers to design customized learning

experiences that cater to the cultural preferences and backgrounds of their students, fostering active participation and enhancing comprehension.

This introduction sets the stage for exploring how the strategic use of diverse technologies can effectively cultivate cross-cultural competence among young learners within the context of English language teaching. By leveraging these tools, educators can empower students to navigate and appreciate the complexities of our globalized world while developing their language skills in meaningful ways.

Materials and methods

People have entered an era of unprecedented electronic information age with the extensive application and advanced development of economic globalization, integration of the world, and modern information technology. The contemporary era has seen a significant rise in the demand for highly skilled individuals adept in foreign language communication, prompting a corresponding increase in the expectations for talent development. This has underscored a fundamental goal within university foreign language education: to cultivate students' practical language proficiency alongside their intercultural communication competence. As societal evolution continues, the frequency of international interactions, particularly in English, has grown noticeably. Thus, embedding relevant and meaningful cultural knowledge into university English programs becomes crucial in fostering natural and fluent communication abilities. Moreover, the importance of studying intercultural communication has never been more pronounced, driven by the expanding global mobility and the widespread adoption of technologies that facilitate cross-cultural exchanges across diverse continents. Therefore, it is wise to consider with due diligence the broader meaning of what we explore, publish, and teach. One critical determinant of successful intercultural communication is undeniably a robust cross-cultural competence. This skill has been firmly integrated into the English syllabus for both English and non-English majors, marking its pivotal role in educational frameworks. The realm of foreign language education has increasingly focused on leveraging advancements in information technologies to bolster these competencies. However, much of the discourse surrounding the development of cross-cultural competence remains theoretical and primarily addresses micro-level issues. Broadly defined, cross-cultural competence equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to effectively engage and communicate in intercultural settings. Proficient individuals possess the capability to understand foreign cultures, perspectives, and behaviors, collaborate with people from diverse backgrounds, adapt to unfamiliar cultural environments, and effectively communicate with international colleagues. Yet, achieving high levels of effectiveness in cross-cultural contexts can be challenging due to various environmental barriers that often confront international business endeavors. The intersection of intercultural communication with social

media amid globalization highlights the dynamic and rapid evolution in this field. Some scholars advocate for a real-time communicative teaching model that involves selecting communication topics, engaging with communicative materials, executing communication based on these topics, and conducting cultural analysis and summaries. However, this approach lacks an evaluation of its educational outcomes. In successful cross-cultural environments, sensitivity to cultural differences is crucial. Neglecting this aspect risks wasting significant time and resources. Mere international experience on a resume does not guarantee intercultural competence; individuals may remain isolated from local cultures during their time abroad, reinforcing rather than diminishing their sense of cultural detachment and superiority. Cross-cultural sensitivity plays a pivotal role in various contexts where interaction with individuals from different cultures is necessary, spanning from performing well in international assignments to engaging in tourism, immigration, and refugee resettlement. This quality is proposed as a significant predictor of success in intercultural environments. Multimedia technologies enhance intercultural communication by broadening its capabilities, introducing diverse models and types, expanding its functions, and gradually lowering barriers to effective cross-cultural communication. Wang and Zhaokuan focused on the theoretical aspect of multimedia technology in intercultural communication but ignored the empirical side of the research. Subsequently, researchers examined the qualities and benefits of multimedia network teaching approaches in education. In teaching college-level English, educators need to focus not only on students' listening, speaking, reading, writing, and translation abilities but also leverage the network's advantages to enhance students' awareness of cultural distinctions and promote the development of cross-cultural competence. Online discussion is a powerful way of the development of critical thinking, collaboration, and reflection and has several benefits for participants of the discussion. The inherent flexibility of Internet-based discussion groups eliminates the constraints of time and place, making courses accessible to students worldwide. However, integrating cross-cultural dynamics into online facilitation poses heightened challenges. Issues such as linguistic misunderstandings, cultural context misinterpretations, and disparities in online engagement further complicate these facilitative processes. Moreover, as businesses expand globally due to economic, political, and market factors, workforce diversity grows. Consequently, there is a growing need for organizational strategies that prioritize the development of employees capable of thriving in cross-cultural work environments. Cross-culturally savvy employees are essential in coordinating and liaising with foreign affiliates both within and outside the organization. For example, a growing number of organizations are relocating top and middle managers to work in countries other than their home country requiring sophisticated cross-cultural interaction skills. In addition to

globalization, the workforce has also become increasingly diverse in terms of race, ethnicity, and nationality even within an organization situated in its home country. The increasing diversity within the workforce underscores the significance of nurturing employees' cross-cultural abilities, even for those not anticipating careers in international firms. Consequently, cross-cultural competence assumes a pivotal role in contemporary society and should be a focal point in the education of students across various disciplines. Moreover, given the integration of interactive technologies into education, it is imperative to harness these tools to cultivate cross-cultural competence effectively. The purposes of this study are to:

- Start an intercultural communication survey among students;
- Identify online programs that universities can utilize to develop cross-cultural competence;
- Formulate recommendations for developing of cross-cultural competence and for utilizing associated online programs.

The term ‘*intercultural competence*’ has existed in the scientific world for more than sixty years however, its single definition and structure is still not formulated. From an analysis of the literature on the topic, it is evident that intercultural competence holds a pivotal position within the framework of core competencies. According to the sources reviewed, V. V. Safonova characterizes intercultural competence as an integral component of an individual's communication skills in language. This underscores the importance of not only linguistic proficiency but also the ability to navigate and engage effectively across different cultural contexts. Intercultural competence, therefore, emerges as a critical aspect of personal and professional development, facilitating meaningful communication and interaction in diverse global settings. The exploration of scientific and pedagogical literature reveals that various scholars have examined and articulated different facets of trainees' intercultural competence in theoretical writings. Researchers such as A.V. Annenkova, V.G. Apalkov, K.E. Bezukladnikov, R.R. Bikiteeva, G.V. Elizarova, O. Leontovich, A.U. Muratov, O.G. Oberemko, L.P. Pavlova, M.V. Plekhanova, I.L. Pluzhnik, A.P. Sadokhin, Y.A. Sinitsina, E.R. Khakimov, A. Artamonova, A.E. Fantini, G. Ellis, E. Jung, T. Nakayama, T.B. Rogers, Y. Sarkees, G. Triandis, and others have contributed significantly to understanding the multidimensional nature of intercultural competence.

According to scholars like N. D. Galskova and N. I. Gez, intercultural competence empowers individuals to engage effectively in cultural interactions, facilitating meaningful intercultural communication. Knapp defines intercultural competence as the ability not only to comprehend other cultures but also to navigate within one's own society with cultural sensitivity. Some scholars emphasize a positive perspective on cultural differences, suggesting that intercultural skills enable

individuals, as described by N. D. Galskova and N. I. Gez, to actively participate and thrive in diverse cultural contexts.

Internationally, scholars such as M. Bennet, G. Chen, D.K. Deardorff, and K. Knapp have contributed to the discourse by analyzing the intricate process of developing intercultural competence. Their studies underscore the complexity involved in nurturing this competency, highlighting its pivotal role in fostering effective intercultural communication and understanding across global contexts. The modern world is characterized by rapid changes driven by globalization, the acceleration of social transformations, the shift towards a post-industrial knowledge society, and a significant increase in intercultural interactions. These changes have underscored the importance of developing a society capable of not only sustaining this rapid growth but also effectively addressing emerging challenges. Education is crucial in shaping this new societal phase. According to Kudabayeva, traditional goals, paradigms, and methods that were relevant a decade ago must give way to new approaches. Previously, educational outcomes focused on students acquiring knowledge, abilities, and skills imparted by teachers. Today, the emphasis is on cultivating individuals who are competent within specific areas of expertise.

Kudrina outlines the structure of intercultural competence into three components: cognitive, activity, and personal. The cognitive component involves understanding the cultural characteristics of both one's own country and the country whose language is being studied. The activity component equips individuals with skills to apply this knowledge in new cultural environments, adapt swiftly to changing circumstances, and communicate effectively using verbal and non-verbal means with people from other cultures. The personal component emphasizes traits such as tolerance, patriotism, and empathy, which are essential for fostering intercultural understanding and cooperation.

The integration of game technologies in education plays a pivotal role in developing intercultural competence. Games make the learning process more dynamic, engaging, and interactive for students at all levels. They provide opportunities for learners to immerse themselves in simulated cultural scenarios, enhancing their ability to navigate and appreciate diverse cultural contexts. This approach not only enriches foreign language communicative competence but also promotes broader cultural understanding and sensitivity among students. Thus, leveraging game technologies in education offers a promising avenue for cultivating the multifaceted skills necessary for effective global citizenship in today's interconnected world.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the incorporation of diverse technologies in English language teaching is not merely advantageous but essential for developing cross-cultural

competence among young learners. These technologies offer a multitude of benefits that traditional teaching methods alone cannot provide. By leveraging digital tools such as virtual reality, online forums, multimedia resources, and interactive apps, educators can create immersive learning environments that expose students to authentic cultural experiences and foster meaningful cross-cultural interactions. Through virtual exchanges and collaborative projects with peers from different backgrounds, students not only improve their language skills but also develop empathy, cultural sensitivity, and a deeper appreciation for diversity.

Furthermore, technology enables educators to personalize learning experiences, catering to individual learning styles and interests while breaking down geographical barriers that limit exposure to diverse cultures. By integrating cultural content into digital resources and using platforms that connect students globally, teachers can promote curiosity about other cultures and encourage students to explore and understand perspectives different from their own. This exposure is crucial in preparing students to communicate effectively and respectfully in multicultural settings, equipping them with invaluable skills for success in an increasingly interconnected world.

Moreover, the use of technology in language teaching empowers students to actively engage with language and culture outside the classroom, transforming passive learning into dynamic, real-world experiences. Whether through virtual tours of cultural landmarks, interactive language games, or multimedia storytelling, technology enriches the learning process by making it more interactive, accessible, and relevant to students' lives. By embracing a wide range of technological tools and platforms, educators can create inclusive learning environments that celebrate diversity and promote global citizenship.

Essentially, incorporating technology strategically into English language teaching not only improves language skills but also nurtures cross-cultural understanding, equipping young learners to excel in an interconnected world. By embracing innovation and harnessing the power of technology, educators can inspire students to become empathetic, culturally aware individuals who contribute positively to a multicultural world.

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